

This paper has been published as: Hideto, M., Hudon, M., & Mersland, R. (2019), “Board Governance: Does Ownership Matter?”, *Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics*, Vol. 91(1), pp. 5-28.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/apce.12262>.
ORCID (Roy Mersland): 0000-0002-6683-2737

Board Governance Does one structure fit all?

Muluneh Hideto ^{a, b} Marek Hudon ^a Roy Mersland ^b

^a *Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB), SBS-EM, CEB, and CERMI, Brussels, Belgium*

^b *Universitetet i Agder, SBL, Kristiansand, Norway*

A B S T R A C T

Good governance is crucial to achieve an organization’s mission. Nevertheless, little is known about how the structure of governance is influenced by the non-profit or for-profit ownership structure of an organization, partly because they tend to be active in different sectors. We solve this challenge by using data from a global sample of 392 microfinance institutions whereof 59 percent are organized as non-profit firms and the remainder have a for-profit ownership structure. Our results show that the average nonprofit organization has larger boards, more female directors, and higher number boards meetings than the for-profit organizations. Moreover, reexamining the effect of board structure on MFI performance, we find that nonprofit microfinance institutions with bigger board size, with more female directors, and convene several board meetings, exhibit better financial performance and reach poorer clients. We thus confirm that ownership structures shape boards and that some board mechanisms are more efficient in some ownership structures than in others. Good board design should thus be sensitive to a firm’s ownership structure.

Keywords: Nonprofit organizations; governance; ownership form; board structure; microfinance institutions

1. Introduction

The research for the link between corporate governance and performance has been a constant topic of the recent academic and non-academic literature. Good governance is crucial to fulfill the mission of an organization. Many scholars have analyzed the impact of the size, composition, and functioning of corporate and nonprofit boards (Andrés-Alonso et al., 2006; Baghat & Black, 1999; Shleifer & Vishny, 1997). While most of these studies draw upon governance practices in the for-profit, publicly traded, large corporations (Zahra & Filatotchev, 2004; Zahra & Hayton, 2005), the literature has been relatively silent on comparison of governance structure and its potentially different outcomes in nonprofit and for-profit organizations (Miller-Millesen, 2003).

The key issue for all these studies has been the identification of an appropriate structure of corporate governance. Although there is no scholarly consensus about how to design and to measure the optimality of for-profit and nonprofit organizations' governance effectiveness, governance effectiveness is an important and meaningful construct that is worthwhile to study. There is a need for evidence to understand if optimal for-profit organization (FPO) governance is the same as or an acceptable substitute for nonprofit organization (NPO) governance. Moreover, it is important that NPOs should take the challenge to develop conceptions and indicators that ground the distinctiveness of NPOs. This is more so important in microfinance where such studies are scant. However, little is known about how governance structure is influenced by the non-profit or for-profit ownership structure of an organization.

Overall, the challenge remains to identify specificities of governance structures for organizations with different ownership types and the key factors explaining these differences (Alexander & Weiner, 1998; Arcot & Brunoy, 2006). Moreover, some authors question if there really is—or can be—an optimal governance design as economic actors choose them in response to the governance issues they face (Adams et al., 2010; Mersland, 2009). Hence, there is a need to respond to the question of whether NPOs and FPOs should design their governance structure differently to fulfill their missions. This paper responds to this research gap.

One key problem when comparing the governance of NPOs with FPOs is that they tend to act on

different markets or with very different clientele. Comparative governance studies are criticized against using data from different industries (Denis & McConnell, 2003). The microfinance industry offers a unique advantage to study this subject since it allows us to base our comparative analysis on NPOs and FPOs that operate in similar markets (Beisland & Mersland, 2013). Microfinance institutions (MFIs) aim at increasing financial inclusion of poor entrepreneurs (Périlleux et al., 2012; Hudon & Sandberg, 2013). Polls of microfinance practitioners highlight that good corporate governance is one of the main challenges in the microfinance sector (CSFI, 2012). Governance is thus crucial and complex in microfinance since MFIs need to combine social impact with financial sustainability. Moreover, some advocate the transformation of nonprofit MFIs into for profit regulated banks arguing that such a shift will improve the governance and make the MFI more efficient (D'Espallier et al., 2017).

We use data from a global sample of 392 MFIs from 74 countries to compare NPO and FPO MFIs' board characteristics, i.e. board size, the number of annual board meetings, and fraction of female directors on boards. Our results support that NPOs compared with FPOs have larger boards, larger fraction of female directors, and higher number board meetings. We also find that these larger boards and size and number of meetings have some clear benefits since they are both positively related with financial performance in NPOs but not FPOs. Moreover, better financial performance in NPOs is achieved thanks to reduced operating expense. This suggests that larger boards that meet more frequently are able to better scrutinize or monitor financial performance.

An increasing number of NPOs are designing their governance based on best practices from for-profit governance model (Helmig et al., 2004). Our results however suggest that nonprofit MFIs do better if they do not follow so called "best practices" of having smaller boards and fewer board meetings. Thus, nonspecific governance guidelines and recommendations applying same criteria for all can damage some firms – in this case the NPOs.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Part two discusses related research on ownership and corporate governance and develops the underlying hypotheses. Part 3 presents the data and the methodology and part 4 lies out and discusses the results. Part 5 concludes.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses

2.1. Ownership types and governance structure

In this section, we discuss related literature and develop hypotheses that motivate our tests and empirical analysis. In the context of shareholder firms, the board is presumed to carry out the monitoring function on behalf of shareholders (John & Senbet, 1998). In nonprofit organizations, the board protects the interests of founders, donors, beneficiaries, and society in general and they are responsible for accomplishing the organization's goals and assure wise usage of resources (Andrés-Alonso et al., 2009).

One important element of corporate governance is board of directors. Board effectiveness is a function of its size, composition and set of rules it adopts in its decision making process. Taking these arguments as our starting point, we examine the size and composition of the boards, along with its interaction with ownership type (nonprofit vs. for-profit). We focus on three important elements related to board effectiveness (John & Senbet, 1998; Adams & Ferreira, 2009); namely board size, fraction of female directors as a measure of board diversity, and number of annual board meetings.

The design of governance is influenced by the nature of the organization's scope and complexity of operations (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Coles et al., 2008), contracting environment (Linck et al., 2008; Harris & Raviv, 2007) and managerial team (Hermalin & Weisbach, 1998; Baker & Gompers, 2003). Nonprofit organizations are not "owned" in the sense of shareholders (Anheier, 2005; Brody, 1996). In essence, the main difference between NPOs and FPOs is that the latter is barred from distributing its net earnings, if any, to individuals who exercise control over it, such as members, officers, directors, or trustees (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Hansmann, 1980).

Though no party has residual rights in NPOs there are stakeholders who may be able to make claim on organization's attention, resources, or output or whose utilities may be affected by the organization's activities (Jegers, 2008). As in FPOs, nonprofit boards are subject to manage the affairs of a nonprofit organization. Yet, the control is carried out without the oversight of shareholders which produces a board fundamentally different from the board of a for-profit firm. The board represents the organization to the outside world and promotes the mission of the organization (Anheier, 2005). In doing so, the nonprofit

board has responsibilities to a range of stakeholders including donors, clients, the public, and even the staff (Labie, 2001; Mersland, 2009). This also makes it more difficult to articulate a single purpose for nonprofit boards. Commonly, board of directors in NPOs assumes the role of resource generation including donations and fund raising, monitoring and oversight over executives, and operational duties (Miller-Millesen, 2003). This represents a much broader set of responsibilities than with for-profit boards. The nonprofits also differ from for-profit organizations in the absence of a takeover market for corporate control that could discipline managers.

2.2. Ownership types and board size

By far the most widely discussed topic in the governance literature is board effectiveness. In for-profit settings, Jensen (1993) suggests that agency problems increase with size. It is generally argued that the problem of shirking from ones responsibility increases as the board size increases, and hampering board effectiveness as a result. Yermack (1996) finds that larger board size predisposes slower decision making and has a significant negative effect on firm performance. Board members may also rarely criticize the policies of top managers and this problem tends to increase with the number of board members (Yermack, 1996).

In nonprofits, the direction of the effect of size of the board on board effectiveness is less clear and more complex. Considering the range of tasks nonprofit boards are trusted with, a board with many directors allows the board more control over operational issues and process larger amounts of information (Oster, 1995). Pearce and Zahra (1989) argue that larger boards can monitor their chief executives' more effectively. Moreover, stakeholders of NPOs often demand being represented and thus increase the size of the board (Pfeffer, 1973; Glaeser, 2003).

Our arguments give rise to Hypotheses 1a and 1b.

Hypothesis 1 a): NPOs have larger boards than FPOs.

Hypothesis 1 b): Having a larger board has a higher positive performance effects in NPOs than in FPOs.

2.3. Ownership types and gender composition

The gender composition of the board is a most used proxy for board diversity (Adams & Ferreira, 2009), and it is well-known that more women on the board increases the board monitoring (Strøm et al., forthcoming). There are however few studies comparing the impact of gender diversity in for-profit and nonprofit boards.

Based on stewardship and democratic model of governance we assume NPO boards to be more gender diverse compared to FPO boards. Stewardship model of governance emphasizes “the capacity and willingness of managers to balance different interests in the professional pursuit of company strategy” (Clarke, 2005, p. 604). The democratic model has at its heart the idea that governance should in fact be the arena for attending to the legitimate interests of all stakeholders through mechanisms such as giving board positions to stakeholder representatives (Donaldson & Preston, 1995; Goodpaster, 1993). Nonprofit governance is built on the notion that governing boards should represent the interests of various stakeholders and the performance of a nonprofit will be judged in part based on who is on their board (Abzug & Galaskiewicz, 2001). Balancing gender in NPOs therefore enables that all perspectives are included in the decision making process. At the opposite, studies show that the gender diversity of boards is generally low in traditional companies, such as FPOs (Huse & Solberg, 2006; Walt & Ingley, 2003).

We assume that gender diversity will have a positive impact on the performance of the MFI. Adams and Ferreira (2009) find that female directors are relatively more effective in monitoring activities than men. They also find a positive effect of women directors upon performance. Similar findings are reported by Smith et al. (2006) and Carter et al. (2003) among others. Our arguments give rise to Hypotheses 2a and 2b.

Hypothesis 2 a): NPOs have a larger fraction of female directors compared to FPOs.

Hypothesis 2 b): Having a larger fraction of female directors has a higher positive performance effect in NPOs compared to FPOs.

2.4. Ownership types and board meetings

The frequency and quality of board meetings represent the board's monitoring diligence in oversight and carries potentially important governance implications (Brick & Chidambaran, 2010; Vafeas, 1999). Adams (2005) uses the number of board and committee meetings as metric for greater degree of board monitoring. Yet, the association between board meeting frequency and performance appears less predictable. Adequate understanding of how individual board members' participation influences overall board performance and factors that promote effective participation are still not well understood (Herman & Renz, 1999). In the nonprofit sector, the board has responsibilities to a range of constituents (Oster, 1995) and expected to not only monitor management, as in the corporate world, but to engage in fund-raising and a range of rather operational tasks (O'Regan & Oster, 2005). Fama and Jensen (1983) advocate that without the threat of takeover market, more active boards should dominate nonprofit boards. Further, frequent board meetings are assumed to happen in firms with more complex conditions. Particularly this should be the case in NPOs. This may justify more frequent meetings than in for-profit organizations.

Considering the range of responsibilities that boards embrace in nonprofit organizations, evidence in this direction would suggest that nonprofits will have frequent board meeting and it is an inexpensive way for them to increase performance. Without frequent meetings, the management team of NPOs would have less support to conduct a variety of tasks. Thus, compared to FPOs (Herman & Renz, 1999) more board meetings will be beneficial for the performance of the NPO. The above discussion leads to Hypothesis 3a and 3b:

Hypothesis 3 a): NPOs have more board meetings compared to FPOs.

Hypothesis 3 b): Having frequent board meetings has a higher positive performance effect in NPOs than in FPOs.

3. Data and Summary Statistics

We test our hypotheses by using a global panel sample of 392 MFIs; whereof 232 are NPOs and 160 are FPOs¹, in 74 countries. Our sample is hand-collected from risk assessment reports conducted by five

¹ In addition to FPOs and NPOs also member-based cooperatives are private suppliers active in the supply of microfinance services. The cooperatives are not included in our analysis since they represent a very distinct ownership type compared to FPOs and NPOs (Mersland, 2009).

major agencies active in rating the performance of MFIs²: MicroRate, Microfinanza, Planet Rating, Crisil, and M-Cril. Each of the five rating agencies is approved to rate and assess MFIs according to the Rating Fund of the Consultative Group to Assist the Poor (CGAP). Each rating yields data for the rating year data together with data for immediately preceding years, up to eight years of data at the maximum.

The use of rating data may introduce sample selection bias. The 478 MFIs in the dataset are probably amongst the largest and best-managed institutions. However, for the comparison of governance in NPOs and FPOs we do not consider the sample bias to be a problem.

Table 2.

Variable definitions.

	<i>Definition</i>
<i>Board structure:</i>	
Board size	Number of directors
Female director	Female directors as fraction of all directors (in %)
Meetings	Number of annual board meetings
<i>Financial performance and cost efficiency:</i>	
ROA (%)	Return on assets = (Net operating income, less taxes)/(period average assets)
OpExp/assets	Operating expense to assets ratio = (Operating expenses)/(annual average assets)
<i>Social performance:</i>	
Women clients (%)	Percentage of an MFI clients that are women
Active borrowers	Total number of active credit clients
<i>MFI and country controls:</i>	
Age	Number of years in operation
Assets	Total amount of assets in thousand of US dollars
Log (Assets)	Logarithm of the total level of assets
Internal audit	Dummy: 1 if MFI has an internal auditor
Internationally initiated	Dummy: 1 if the MFI was initiated by an international actor
HDI	Human development index. HDI is a composite statistic of life expectancy, education, and income per capita indicators.
Economic freedom	Heritage Foundation's index of economic freedom. It measures economic freedom of countries based on trade freedom, business freedom, investment freedom, and property rights
GDP per capita	GDP per capita is gross domestic product divided by midyear population.
Region controls	Dummy: dummies for five world regions: Africa, Asia, East Europe, Latin America, and Middle East and North Africa (Africa has been taken as reference category)

² Other articles using databases from rating agencies are, for instance, Gutiérrez-Nieto et al. (2007), Beisland and Mersland (2012), Hudon and Traça (2011), Garmaise and Natividad (2010), Hartarska and Mersland (2012), or Strøm, Ø., D'Espallier, B. & Mersland, R. (forthcoming).

Extant literature has shown that firm level characteristics and economic conditions across countries influence institutional incentives, efficiency, and performance (John & Senbet, 1998; Hartarska & Mersland, 2012; Labie & Mersland, 2011). Thus, we have control variables at both the country and MFI levels. We control firm-level differences by incorporating two much used control variables in MFI research namely firm size and firm age. In addition we include a dummy for whether the MFI was initiated by an international actor and whether it has an internal auditor reporting to the board since these are important conditions in MFI governance (Mersland & Strøm, 2009). As country controls we include the Economic freedom index, Human Development Index, and the GDP per Capita.

Table 2 presents the definitions with the respective measurement parameters for our dependent, explanatory, and control variables.

3.1. Description of the data

Descriptive statistics of variables used in the analysis are set out in table 3. The rating reports are not uniform in data included resulting in different number of firm-year observations. 59 percent of the MFIs are NPOs illustrating the important influence of nonprofit firms in the microfinance industry. At the same time having 41 percent being FPO provides a relatively well balanced setting for the testing of differences between NPOs and FPOs.

On average boards in MFIs meet eight times per year and have 7 members whereof women take up 28 percent of the seats. These numbers are in line with numbers reported in Hartarska and Mersland (2012). 48 percent of the MFIs have an internal auditor reporting to the board while 40 percent of the MFIs were initiated by an international actor demonstrating the high international influence in this industry (Mersland et al., 2011). The average MFI has been in business for 10 years, and has around 11 million US dollars in assets. Thus, both age-wise and size-wise the average MFI should have established a thought through governance system. Interesting, microfinance is today a banking business practiced in diverse countries illustrated by the fact that the HDI range from 0.05 to 0.81.

Table 3.

Table 3 reports the summary statistics of our board structure, MFI and country variables for the sample.

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
<i>Board characteristic</i>					
Board size	1388	6.872	2.93	2	23
Female director	698	0.271	0.239	0	1
#Meetings	987	7.09	7.08	1	52
<i>MFI characteristic</i>					
NPO/FPO	1876	0.592	0.492	0	1
ROA	1776	0.020	0.104	-0.669	0.56
OpExp/assets ratio	1517	0.227	0.156	0.039	1.712
%Women	347	0.691	0.254	0	1
Active borrowers	1786	35330.98	341904.7	24	9200000
Assets (US\$ 000s)	1842	11400	24300	19.288	280000
Ln (Assets)	1842	15.180	1.470	9.87	19.45
Internationally initiator	1805	0.427	0.495	0.00	1.00
Internal auditor	1264	0.538	0.499	0.00	1.00
Age	1858	9.863	6.246	1.00	79.00
<i>Macroeconomic control variables</i>					
HDI	1384	0.611	0.130	0.06	0.81
Economic freedom	1347	56.39	6.056	29.4	77.8
GDP per capita	1466	1828.075	1894.928	120	11434

We focus on the two dimensions of MFI performance namely financial and social performance. As for the bottom line financial performance we observe that the average MFI report a low but positive ROA of 2 percent. The high operational costs in operating MFIs is a major concern in the industry (Mersland & Strøm, 2010) and is here demonstrated by the fact that the average MFI has an expense ratio of 24 percent. Our two proxies for social performance are percentage of female clients and number of clients served which are indicators of the so-called depth of outreach and breath of outreach respectively (Mersland & Strøm, 2010; D'Espallier, Hudon, & Szafarz, 2013). The average MFI in our dataset serves around 32 thousand clients whereof 67 percent are women.

Table 4.

Correlation matrix

#	Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1.	Board size	1									
2.	Female director	0.03	1								
3.	Meetings	0.01	-0.04	1							
4.	NGO	0.21	0.24	0.13	1						
5.	Internal audit	-0.02	-0.124	0.103	-0.18	1					
6.	Age	0.11	0.1	0.29	0.13	0.128	1				
7.	Ln (Assets)	0.05	-0.09	0.17	-0.15	0.422	0.359	1			
8.	Internationally initiator	0.001	0.02	-0.22	-0.03	0.018	-0.139	0.012	1		
9.	HDI	-0.04	-0.08	0.17	0.20	0.055	-0.029	0.11	-0.06	1	
10.	Economic freedom	-0.04	-0.09	0.01	-0.07	-0.039	0.012	0.046	0.07	-0.02	1
11.	GDP per capita	-0.02	-0.02	0.08	0.09	-0.095	0.005	0.1	-0.104	0.643	0.07

We run multivariate panel data regressions to analyze relationships between governance and performance variables. In order to check for multicollinearity, we run a correlation analysis for the explanatory variables. Kennedy (2008) puts the threshold level for multicollinearity at about 0.80. We find no variables to reach this level. The result suggests that our governance and MFI performance variables can be run independently.

3.2. Methods

We apply three different tests to explore the differences in governance mechanisms between nonprofit and for-profit MFIs. First, we apply univariate t-test to analyze the differences in mean value between the nonprofit and for-profit MFI groups on the three hypothesized governance variables (board size, female fraction and board meetings). Second, to further substantiate the result of the univariate t-test we regress our governance variables against the predictor variable of dummy for nonprofit NGOs and SHFs with selected set of control variables. In this case, we use the random-effects (RE) model for our board variables including board size, female directors ratio, and board meetings. We use the RE model considering the

time-invariant nature of several of the covariates (Wooldridge, 2002). Our basic estimating board structure relations is as follows:

$$\mathbf{x}_{(i,t)} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \mathbf{NPO} + \alpha_i \mathbf{Controls} + e_{(i,t)} \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_{(i,t)} = \phi_0 + \phi_1 \mathbf{NPO} + \phi_2 \mathbf{x} + \phi_i \mathbf{Controls} + e_{(i,t)} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{z}_{(i,t)} = \eta_0 + \eta_1 \mathbf{NPO} + \eta_2 \mathbf{x} + \eta_i \mathbf{Controls} + e_{(i,t)} \quad (3)$$

where X represents MFI board size, Y represents MFI fraction of female directors, Z represents number of annual board meetings, and NPO represent dummy if the MFI ownership type is a nonprofit organization. $Controls$ represent MFI characteristics and country-level macroeconomic indicators.

Third, to achieve the objective of the study that relates to whether nonprofit organizations adopt a governance mechanism that is optimal to their (institutional) context, we regress the performance variables on the governance variables and selected control variables. To identify the effect of ownership in this case, our regression follow that for each board variable we introduce the interaction variable of ownership status for NPO, which combines the effect of both the governance and ownership type on the performance measures.

We estimate simultaneous equations (equation 4) in all our performance regressions, board size, fraction of female directors, and number of annual board meetings using three-stage least squares (3SLS) regressions. This is similar to Coles et al. (2008) and Bhagat and Black (2001) who estimate Tobin's Q, board composition, and CEO ownership using 3SLS. Our simultaneous equation specifications for investigating this relation is

$$\Pi_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^N \beta_j \mathbf{x} + \sum_{k=1}^N \beta_k \mathbf{y} + \sum_{l=1}^N \beta_l \mathbf{z} + \sum_{m=1}^N \beta_m \mathbf{NPO} + \mathbf{Controls} + \varepsilon_i \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{(i,t)} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \Pi_{(t-1)} + \alpha_2 \mathbf{NPO} + \alpha_i \mathbf{Controls} + e_{(i,t)}$$

$$\mathbf{y}_{(i,t)} = \phi_0 + \phi_1 \Pi_{(t-1)} + \phi_2 \mathbf{NPO} + \phi_3 \mathbf{x} + \phi_i \mathbf{Controls} + e_{(i,t)}$$

$$\mathbf{z}_{(i,t)} = \eta_0 + \eta_1 \Pi_{(t-1)} + \eta_2 \mathbf{NPO} + \eta_3 \mathbf{x} + \eta_i \mathbf{Controls} + e_{(i,t)}$$

where Π represents the four MFI performance measures—*ROA*, *OpExp to assets ratio*, *%women clients*, and *log of number of active borrowers*. X represents MFI board size, Y represents MFI fraction of female directors, Z represents number of annual board meetings, and NPO represent dummy if the MFI ownership type is nongovernment organization. *Controls* represent MFI characteristics and country-level macroeconomic indicators.

In our regressions of MFI performance, we use board size, fraction of female directors, and number of annual board meetings as explanatory variables. We recognize that all of these variables can be endogenous, in which case our board structure variables, in turn, are determined by performance (Coles et al., 2008). To reduce endogeneity problems we use simultaneous equations in our empirical analysis (Boubaker et al., 2012). Our 3SLS structural model takes into account endogeneity arising from the simultaneous determination between our governance and performance variables. Moreover, lagged performance variables are used as an instrument to control for the impact of prior performance on current performance, which is in the spirit of controlling for dynamic endogeneity (Wooldridge, 2002). We also use the logarithm of the board size, number of female directors, and annual number of board meetings. In taking the log, we assume that the effect of these variables is non-linear in that the efficacy of board structure exhibits decreasing returns to scale (Coles et al., 2008).

Finally, we use NPOs as interaction terms to capture the moderating effect of ownership type on the relation between our performance and board variables.

4. Econometric results

In this section, we start out by presenting univariate results for the differences in board characteristics between NPOs and FPO followed by multivariate testing of the same relationship. Finally, we present econometric results on the moderating effect of ownership on the relation between board structure and MFI performance.

4.1. Univariate results

Table 5 presents clear evidence that there seem to be significant differences between NPOs and FPOs in the way they organize their boards. While the average NPO has 7.35 directors, the average FPO has 6.1.

Likewise, an NPO board meets much more frequently compared to a FPO board, 7.8 times a year compared to six respectively. One plausible reason for the larger board meeting more frequently could be that nonprofit organization boards assume broader and more complex set of responsibilities than the for-profit boards (Wirtz, 2011; O'Regan & Oster, 2005). Moreover, the larger board size could indicate more stakeholder representation (Andrés-Alonso et al., 2006). Table 5 further indicates a significant difference in the gender composition of the boards between NPOs and FPOs. While only one of every five board member in an FPO is a woman, the ratio is 1 to 3 in NPOs. Univariate testing only provide hints of differences on board characteristics between NPOs and FPOs. We therefore now turn to multivariate testing.

Table 5.

Univariate results. Table 5 reports the means of board characteristics for MFIs based on nonprofit and for-profit ownership status. *Board size* is the number of directors. *Female director* is the fraction of female directors to the number of all directors. *#Meetings* is number of annual board meetings. Significant at the *** 1%, ** 5% and * 10% level.

Variable	Nonprofits	For-Profits	t-statistic
	Mean (Std. Dev.)	Mean (Std. Dev.)	
Board size	7.351 (3.3)	6.120 (1.96)	-7.79***
Female director	0.315 (0.24)	0.194 (0.21)	-6.603***
Meetings	7.774 (8.1)	5.901 (4.6)	-4.03***
Internal audit	0.467 (0.5)	0.647 (0.5)	6.34***

4.2 Multivariate results: effects of ownership type on board structure

We now extend our analysis to a multivariate setting using Random Effects GLS regression and including control variables to explore the effect of the ownership status on the MFI's board size, female directors ratio and number of annual board meetings. The results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6.

Ownership type and board structure differences

<i>Variables</i>	Board size	Female dir.	#Meetings
NPO	4.162***	0.118**	6.187**
<i>Firm /country controls</i>			
Internal audit	0.324	-0.033	1.755
Age	-0.102*	0.010**	-0.169*
Ln (Total assets)	0.206*	-0.018	0.346**
Int. initiated	0.277	0.042	-2.47***
HDI	4.099	-0.097	-1.560
Economic freedom	-0.016	-0.004	0.014
Regional dummies ³	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>
_cons	2.173	0.692**	-2.309
<i>Model statistics:</i>			
<i>N</i>	849	437	609
Wald chi2	26.28	23.7	50.91
Prob > chi2	0.0059	0.0141	0
R-squared	0.3146	0.0518	0.4929

Significant at the *** 1% level, ** 5% level, and * 10% level.

Consistent with our univariate test for the mean difference between nonprofit MFIs and for-profit MFIs, the GLS regression in Table 6 reveals significant positive influence of the NPO ownership status on the MFI's board characteristics also when firm and country controls are included in the analysis. NPOs have larger boards, a higher fraction of female members and meet more frequently compared to FPOs. These results are consistent with the hypothesis that NPOs operate under greater influence of stakeholders and their boards assume more responsibilities than for-profit boards. Table 6 further reveals interesting findings for some of the control variables. The finding that boards of internationally initiated MFIs meet less frequently than nationally initiated MFIs is probably a consequence of the large geographical distance for international board members to attend meeting. Another finding attracting our attention is that boards seem

³ Region 1 representing Africa has been left out as reference category.

to meet less frequently in more developed countries (higher HDI and Freedom index) which could indicate that formal institutions, like for instance better regulations, to some extent substitute board governance. The finding that larger MFIs engage fewer women on their boards could be a sign of thin high quality labor markets available for board positions in more complex organizations. This is an area that should attract interest of researchers.

4.3. Multivariate results: effect of board structure on performance

Our results in the preceding section highlight the existence of board governance difference among the nonprofit and for-profit MFIs operating in similar markets. In itself, this is interesting because it demonstrates that firms design their governance not only according to the markets in which they operate but also according to the stakeholder pressure they experience (Mori & Mersland, 2014) and the ownership – management incentive problems they are facing (Mayers & Smith, 2005). Thus, our paper contributes to the literature that governance design arises endogenously according to the governance challenges firms have (Adams et al., 2010). However, the question that remains is whether the difference in governance design between NPOs and FPOs influences the performance outcomes of the firms. This is the question we try to address in this section.

Thus, we now explore the relation between board size, fraction of female directors and number of annual board meetings on MFI performance for nonprofit and shareholder owned MFIs. As outlined in the method section we consider key financial (ROA), cost efficiency (OpExp/assets) and social performance (breadth of outreach – number of credit clients and depth of outreach - % female clients) indicators of MFIs. To account for the ownership effect of the board governance mechanisms on the performance of MFI, we introduce in our model the interaction term of the board structure variables—board size, female directors ratio board meetings – with the NPO ownership type. Table 7 reports the results of our multivariate 3SLS regressions. The interesting variables to notice are the three interaction explanatory variables.

We observe that explanatory power for the different models are at satisfying levels. The results are interesting and. In column A, the ROA regressions, we observe that all three board variables change the direction of influence while remaining significant when the interaction variable is introduced. Thus, while

larger boards meeting more frequently is generally negative for the performance of the MFI such board features are positive if applied in NPOs. Thus, while FPOs should keep their boards smaller and not meet too frequently NPOs should do the opposite. Hypotheses 1b and 3 b are supported.

Somewhat surprising in column A; while FPOs benefit from having more female members in their boards NPOs do not experience such positive outcome of gender diversity in their boards. However, the initially surprising finding for the female board fraction in NPOs might not be so surprising after all when considering the social dimensions of the MFI's performance reported in column 3 and 4. Larger fractions of female directors in NPOs are associated with the outreach to more clients in general and more female clients. Thus, it looks like female directors, largely than male directors, trade-off financial performance with social performance when sitting on NPO boards. The other results of the interaction terms in relation to the social performance variables are generally not significant. The only exception is the surprising finding that a higher number of board meetings in NPOs is associated with lower outreach to female clients. The result is however only weakly significant and should thus be interpreted with care.

Table 7.

Multivariate 3SLS regressions

<i>Independent Variables</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>D</i>
	ROA	OpExp/ Assets	Women Clients	Log (borrowers)
Board size	-0.006**	-0.01**	-0.005	0.069*
Board size x NPO	0.007*	0.003	0.015	-0.008
Female dir. Ratio	0.032	-0.076*	0.06	-0.993***
Female dir. x NPO	-0.11**	0.065	0.184**	2.055***
#Meetings	-0.022**	0.002	0.001	0.015
#Meetings x NPO	0.001*	-0.002	-0.014*	-0.02
NPO	-0.031	0.024	0.155	-0.055
Internal audit dummy	-0.02*	0.048***	0.006	0.623***
Age	-0.001*	-0.002**	0.004	0.026***
Ln (Total assets) ⁴	0.04***	-0.039***	-0.028	
Int. initiated	-0.014	0.019	-0.005	0.749**
HDI	0.135	0.416**	-0.366	-3.013
Economic freedom	-0.003***	0.001	0.000	-0.005
GDP per cap	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000***
Regional dummies ⁵	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>
_cons	-0.386***	0.476**	1.154*	7.44***
Model statistics				
<i>Obs.</i>	406	404	90	405
<i>R-sq.</i>	0.247	0.173	0.441	0.363
<i>F-Stat</i>	7.05	4.48	3.11	7.67
<i>p-value</i>	0	0	0	0

Values of t-statistics based on robust standard errors are reported in parentheses. Significant at the *** 1% level, ** 5% level, and * 10% level.

Table 7 further shows that ownership per se does not seem to influence the performance of the MFI. This goes against typical recommendations in the industry that NPO-MFIs should transform into shareholder owned banks (for an overview of the MFI transformation literature see D'Espallier et al., 2017) though it is in line with earlier findings reported in the microfinance academic literature (Mersland & Strøm,

⁴ Largely the variation in the number of active borrowers is explained by the total assets of an MFI. Thus to avoid exaggerated R-sq, we excluded this variable in the log(borrowers) regression.

⁵ Region 1 representing Africa has been left out as reference category.

2008). Another finding worth reporting are the positive effect of having an international initiator on the outreach to more clients. This is in line with Mersland et al., (2011) who show that international actors have a positive effect on the MFI's social performance and a neutral effect on the MFI's financial performance. It is also interesting to notice that as MFIs grow older they do not seem to trade-off social performance with financial performance – a claim often mentioned in the literature (Hermes et al., 2011). The results in table 7 indicate that the age of the MFI is associated with the outreach to more clients and to a reduction in the ROA. Thus, our finding is in line with Mersland and Strøm (2010) who do not find evidence of mission drift among MFIs. What seems for certain is that the mission drift debate in the microfinance literature will and should continue. Finally, the improved ROA related with the size of the MFI is in line with Hartarska et al, (2013) who demonstrate the scale economies related with the supply of microfinance services.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we do two things. We first test the Adams et al., and Mayers and Smith notion that board governance design is different depending on ownership type of the firm. Since MFIs, whether organized as Nonprofits or For-profit, operating in similar markets the microfinance industry offers a unique testing ground to test this notion. Second, we test whether the differences in board governance design has performance effects for the MFI depending on its ownership status. In line with theory we find that the average nonprofit organization has larger boards, more female directors, and make more frequent boards meetings compared with for-profit organizations. We further show that the negative performance effect from having larger boards having frequent meetings is offset and turned into a positive effect when applied in nonprofit MFIs. Moreover, we present evidence that boards with a larger fraction of female directors seem to trade-off financial performance with improved social performance.

These findings assume significance as it offers another look at the role of boards in the governance of NPOs and assess its performance effect therefrom. Our evidence support the argument that for-profit and nonprofit organizations have different motives to operate and, therefore, that they should be approach their governance choices differently. We find evidence that a measure of board structure, which takes into account heterogeneity in governance choices between NPO and FPO, is positively associated with MFI performance. Our analysis provides support for the principle that in corporate governance one-size-does-

not-fit-all. On the contrary, mere adherence to general "best practices" of good governance is not necessarily associated with superior performance.

From a policy perspective, we highlight that prescribing FPO governance structure and mechanical adherence of this by NPOs may not be in the best interest of the later. Our findings suggest that more research is required before adopting such recommendations, which are based on a notion that there is one optimal board size or board composition. Moreover, NPO MFIs appear to transform to FPOs and it is intriguing to study how the governance of NPOs evolve in the due process of the transformation.

References

- Abzug, R. & Galaskiewicz, J. (2001). Non-profit boards: crucibles of expertise or symbols of local identities? *Non-profit & Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 30(1) 51-73.
- Adams, R. B., B. E. Hermalin & M. S. Weisbach (2010). The role of boards of directors in corporate governance: a conceptual framework & survey. *Journal of Economic Literature* 48 (1), 58–107.
- Adams, R., (2005). What do boards do? Evidence from board committee and director compensation data. Working Paper. Stockholm School of Economics.
- Adams, R.B., Ferreira, D. (2009). Women in the boardroom and their impact on governance and performance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 94(2), 291–309.
- Alexander, J. A. & Weiner, B. J. (1998). The adoption of the corporate governance model by nonprofit organizations. *Nonprofit Management & Leadership* 8(3), 223–242.
- Andrés-Alonso, P., Azofra-Palenzuela, V., & Romero-Merino, E. (2009). Determinants of nonprofit board size and composition. The case of Spanish Foundation. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 38(5), 784-809.
- Andrés, P., Martín, N., & Romero, M. E. (2006). The governance of nonprofit organizations: Empirical evidence from nongovernmental development organizations in Spain. *Nonprofit and voluntary sector quarterly*, 35, 588-604.
- Anheier, H. K. (2005). *Nonprofit organizations: Theory, management, and policy*. London, UK: Routledge.
- Arcot, S. R. & Brunoy, V. G. (2006). One size does not fit all, after all: Evidence from Corporate Governance. Financial Markets Group, London School of Economics, London.
- Baghat, S., & Black, B. (1999). "The uncertain relationship between board composition and firm performance." *Business Lawyer*, 54, 921-963.
- Baker, M. & P. A. Gompers (2003). "The determinants of board structure at the initial public offering." *Journal of Law & Economics* 46 (2), 569–98.
- Beisland, L. A., & Mersland, R. (2013). Earnings quality in the microfinance industry. In J. P. Gueyie, R. Manos, & J. Yaron. (Eds.), *Microfinance in developing and developed countries: Issues, policies and performance evaluation* (pp. 83-106). Hampshire, UK: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Bhagat, S., Black, B., 2002. The non-correlation between board independence and long-term firm performance. *Journal of Corporation Law* 27, 231–274.
- Boubaker, Sabri, Bang Dang Nguyen, Duc Khuong Nguyen (2012). *Corporate Governance: Recent Developments and New Trends*. Springer Science & Business Media Publisher.
- Brick, I., & Chidambaran, N.K. (2010). Board meetings, committee structure, and firm value. *Journal of Corporate Finance* 16, 533–553
- Brody, E. (1996). "Agents without principals: The economic convergence of the nonprofit and for-profit organizational forms". *New York Law School Law Review*, 40, 457-528.

- Carter, D.A., Simkins, B.J., Simpson, W.G. (2003). "Corporate governance, board diversity and firm value". *Financial Review* 38, 33-53.
- Clarke, T. (2005). "Accounting for Enron: Shareholder value and stakeholder interests." *Corporate Governance*, 13(5), 598-612.
- Coles, J.L., Daniel, N.D. & Naveen, L. (2008). "Boards: Does one size fit all?" *Journal of Financial Economics* 87, 329–356
- CSFI (2012). Microfinance banana skins staying relevant. The CSFI survey of microfinance risk. New York.
- D'Espallier, B., Goedecke, J., Hudon, M., & Mersland, R., (2017), "From NGOs to banks: Does institutional transformation alter the business model of microfinance institutions?" *World Development*, 89, 19-33.
- D'Espallier, B., Hudon, M., & Szafarz, A. (2013). "Unsubsidized microfinance institutions." *Economics Letters*, 120(2), 174–176.
- Denis, D.K. and J. McConnell (2003). International corporate governance. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 38 (1), 1-36.
- Donaldson, L. & Preston, M. (1995). The stakeholder theory of the corporation: concepts, evidence, and implications. *Academy of Management Review*, 20(1), 85-91.
- Fama, E. & Jensen, M. (1983). Separation of ownership and control. *Journal of Law & Economics*, 26, 301–26.
- Glaeser, E. (2003). The governance of nonprofit firms, in Edward Glaeser, ed., *The governance of nonprofit firms*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Goodpaster, K. (1993). Business ethics and stakeholder analysis, in Winkler, E. and Coombs, J. (Eds), *Applied Ethics: A Reader*, Blackwell, Oxford, 229-48.
- Hansmann, H. (1980). The role of the nonprofit enterprise. *Yale Law Journal*, 89, 835–901.
- Harris, M., & A. Raviv (2008). A theory of board control and size. *Review of Financial Studies* 21 (4), 1797–1832.
- Hartarska, V. & Mersland, R. (2012). What governance mechanisms promote efficiency in reaching poor clients? Evidence from rated microfinance institutions. *European Financial Management* 18(2), 218-239.
- Hartarska, V., Shen, X. & Mersland, R., (2013), "Scale Economies and Input Price Elasticities in Microfinance Institutions." *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 37(1), 118-131
- Helmig, B., Jegers, M. & Lapsley, I. (2004): Challenges in Managing Nonprofit Organizations: A Research Overview. *Voluntas: International Journal of Voluntary and Nonprofit Organizations*, 15(2), pp.101-116.
- Hermalin, B.E., Weisbach, M.S. (1998). "Endogenously chosen boards of directors and their monitoring of the CEO." *American Economic Review* 88 (1), 96–118.
- Herman, R. D., & Renz, D. O. 1999. Theses on nonprofit organizational effectiveness. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 28: 107-126.
- Hermes N., Lensink, R. & Meesters, A. (2011). Outreach and efficiency of microfinance institutions. *World Development* 39(6) 938-948.
- Hudon, M. & Périlleux, A. (2013). Surplus Distribution and Characteristics of Social Enterprises: Evidence from Microfinance, *Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*.
- Huse, M. & Solberg, A. G. (2006). Gender-related boardroom dynamics: How Scandinavian women make and can make contributions on corporate boards. *Women in Management Review*, 21(2), 113-130.
- Jegers, M. (2008). *Managerial economics of non-profit organizations*. London, UK: Routledge.
- Jensen, M. (1993). The modern industrial revolution, exit and the failure of internal control systems. *Journal of Finance*, 48, 831–80.
- John, K. & L.W. Senbet (1998). Corporate governance and board effectiveness. *Journal of Banking & Finance* 22, 371-403.
- Kennedy, P. (2008) *A Guide to Econometrics*, 6th ed., Blackwell Publishing, Malden, Mass. Kennedy (2008)
- Labie, M (2001). Corporate governance in microfinance organizations: A long and winding road. *Management Decision*, 39(4), 296–301.
- Labie, M. & Mersland, R. (2011). Corporate governance challenges in microfinance. In Armendáriz, B. & Labie, M. (Eds.), *The Handbook of Microfinance*, London: World Scientific Publishing Ltd., 283–300.
- Mayers, D. and C. W. Smith (2005). Agency problems and the corporate charter. *Journal of Law, Economics, and Organization* 21(2), 417-440.

- Mersland, R & RØ Strøm (2008). Performance and trade-offs in microfinance institutions—does ownership matter? *Journal of International Development*, 20, 598–612.
- Mersland, R & RØ Strøm (2009). Performance and governance in microfinance institutions. *Journal of Banking and Finance* 33, 662–669.
- Mersland, R. (2009). The cost of ownership in microfinance organizations. *World Development* 37(2), 469-478.
- Mersland, R., Randøy, T., & Strøm, R.Ø. (2011). The impact of international influence on microbanks' performance: a global survey. *International Business Review* 20(2), 163–176.
- Mersland, R., RØ Strom, R. Oystein (2010). Microfinance mission drift? *World Development* 38(1), 28-36.
- Miller-Millesen, L. (2003). Understanding the behaviour of non-profit boards of directors: A theory-based approach. *Non-profit & Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 32(4), 521–547.
- Mori, N. & Mersland, R. (2014). “Boards in microfinance organizations: do stakeholders matter?” *Journal of Management and Governance* 18(1), 285–313.
- O'Regan, K. & Oster, S. (2005). Does government funding alter nonprofit governance? *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 21, 359–79.
- Oster, S. (1995). *The strategic management of nonprofit organizations*. New York: Oxford Press.
- Pearce, J. A., & Zahra, S. A. (1989). Boards of directors and corporate financial performance: A review and integrative model. *Journal of Management*, 15(2), 291–334.
- Pérelleux, A., Hudon, M., & Bloy, E. (2012). Surplus distribution in microfinance: differences among cooperative, nonprofit, and shareholder forms of ownership, *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 41 (3), 386-404.
- Pfeffer, J. (1973). Size, composition, and functions of hospital boards of directors: A study of organization-environment linkage. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 18, 349-363.
- Shleifer, A., Vishny, R. (1997). A survey of corporate governance. *Journal of Finance* 52, 737–783.
- Smith, N., Smith, V., & Verner, M. (2006). Do women in top management affect firm performance? A panel study of 2,500 Danish firms. *Journal of Productivity & Performance Management*, 55(7), 569-593.
- Vafeas, N. (1999). Board meeting frequency and firm performance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 53, 113–142.
- Walt, N. & Ingley, C. (2003). Board dynamics and the influence of professional background, gender and ethnic diversity of directors. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 11(3), 218-234.
- Wirtz, P. (2011). The cognitive dimension of corporate governance in fast growing entrepreneurial firms. *European Management Journal*, 29, 431–447.
- Wooldridge J. (2002) *Econometric analysis of cross section and panel data*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Yermack, D. (1996). Higher market valuation of companies with a small board of directors. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 40(2), 185–211.
- Zahra, S. & Filatotchev, I. (2004). Governance of the entrepreneurial threshold firm: A knowledge-based perspective. *Journal of Management Studies*, 41(5), 887–897.
- Zahra, S. & Hayton, J. (2005). Organizational lifecycle transitions and their consequences for the governance of entrepreneurial firms: An analysis of start-up and adolescent high-technology new ventures. In I. Filatotchev & M. Wright (Eds.), *The life cycle of corporate governance*. Edward Elgar.